

CHARACTERISTICS OF UZBEK FOLK APPLIED ARTS AND THEIR PLACE IN SOCIETY

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Annotation: Applied art of our people in the history of culture of Uzbekistan, its special place, artistic design, the orientation of folk art to the art of decoration. Opinions about the characteristics of art forms and their place in society are cracked.

Keywords: applied arts,, decorative painting, folk art, decorative arts,, Handicrafts, features of applied decorative arts, pottery, tile colors, "drawing" and "pencil", Islamic pattern.

INTRODUCTION

It is known that folk art in Uzbekistan is developing on the basis of using the best aspects of culture, which it has been able to create throughout its history. In the history of culture of Uzbekistan, the applied and artistic art of our people has a special place. In the past, painting and sculpture were virtually destroyed under the pressure of Islam. Instead, artistic design took center stage, directing folk art to the path of decoration. The multifaceted artistic talent of our people was reflected in the various works of art of craftsmen, in the wonderful works of architects.

In its history, the Uzbek people have created world-class, unique works of artistic, monumental and applied art. These works still have their own high artistic style. The beauty and elegance of its forms testify to the fact that the creator was a delicate and thoughtful artist. See these stunning landscapes in the interiors and exteriors of buildings, in the elegant tiles, in the embossed ganch houses, in the intricate patterns carved in stone and wood, in the attractive colors of carpets, king-atlases, suzans in various flowers made of metal and leather possible. The aesthetic

quality of applied art is the culture of making vital items, which are widely used not only in rugs, but also in the decoration of houses, architectural structures, gardens and alleys. All kinds of household utensils - chairs and tables, dishes, clothes, carpets, suzani and embroidery, jewelry, toys, etc. are all the applied and artistic art of our people.

It also includes examples of tiling, painting, stone carving, wood carving used in the interior and exterior decoration of buildings. The difference between works of applied art and other types of fine arts is that they express the content of their artistic image in the performance of these functions, without losing their specific practical properties.

Ancient cities of Uzbekistan Afrosiyob, Varakhsha. Fragments of pottery found during archeological excavations in Poykent confirm that in the past most household items were made of pottery. The Uzbek people have a rich tradition in this area, which has a large number of pottery centers. It is clear that pottery in the territory of Uzbekistan dates back to ancient times. is one of the art forms. Glazed and plain baked lo \ or ceramics are widely used in Uzbek life.

The invention of the wheel in pottery in antiquity is one of the great achievements of the production of the ancient period. But along with meeting the potential needs of man, ceramics is becoming an area that meets human aesthetic requirements. Man tries to beautify household booms. Thus ceramic production will rise to the level of ceramic art. This prosthesis is on earth and inclusive

It dates back to ancient times, to the Neolithic period in Uzbekistan. During the Bronze Age, in the 2000s BC, tile colors were invented in pottery. It was found in the Kyzyl-Kir oasis of Bukhara and in the city of Chust in Fergana. Pottery is a sign. The surface of pots, pans, plates and bowls is very well processed. iUi is a masterpiece of dark brown triangular mesh, kungura and dandona-shaped ornaments on light red. According to ancient researchers, these ornaments have a certain meaning. The Ancient Period, which endowed many works of art, showed how much perseverance and assertiveness in the field of pottery. One of such items is kept in the Museum of History of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan. Found in Termez

in the early twentieth century. This vessel, which resembles an ancient Greek vessel, has embossed images. During the heyday of feudal craftsmanship in the IX-XII centuries, cities competed with each other in manufacturing crafts. Craftsmen's associations show off their masters and equate them with famous doctors, poets, and religious leaders. The works of these masters are exhibited not only throughout the city, but also abroad. Highly decorated ceramics not only meet the daily needs of the people, but also make people's lives more elegant and decorate the hotel's terraces as a work of art that they watch.

It is known that in the following centuries, the art of pottery in all regions of Uzbekistan is experiencing periods of extinction and development. But the decorative-artistic traditions will continue, and the XIX century will give us wonderful ceramics, which will have a unique local style and school in every part of Uzbekistan. Today there are two types of Central Asian pottery. This is hand-made glazed pottery, which, although geographically socially developed, is very high in terms of artistic quality. This proves that it is possible to create very, very high-quality items in a simple way.

Glazed ceramics is an art of farming with a developed culture. It is created on a wheel and the products are created in a relatively light, elegant, high-quality way. The village of Rishtan in the Fergana Valley has become famous not only in Uzbekistan but also abroad for its pottery. As early as the 19th century, Rishtan pottery laid the foundation for pottery in Namangan, Andijan, Asaka and other regions of the Fergana Valley. When decorating items, Fergana craftsmen create interesting combinations with geometric patterns, skillfully intertwining plant-like islams. Often these are circular shields that intersect with each other. It is characteristic that Fergana masters create combinations that confirm the top and bottom of the items.

When talking about Fergana pottery, it is necessary to emphasize the blue color in the items. In the East, blue is the color of happiness. It is the color of the sky and the water. And water has always been a symbol of happiness in this country. In general, Fergana pottery gives an argan impression. The pottery of Khorezm and

Karakalpakstan differs by its extensive use of turquoise and white colors. But there is a different impression here than in Fergana. Pure ornamental method prevails in the decoration of Khorezmian items. These patterns have linear and intricate graphics.

In Tashkent, "drawing" and "pencil" methods are currently used together. Tashkent potters create wonderful things. Vases and plates with pictures of great scholars and classics of Uzbek literature are considered to be rare works of art. , the production of ceramic bowls is developing rapidly. There are several different floral compositions in Tashkent ceramics. Pottery decorated with simple flowers is called "simple" and "dry". There is also a composition called "pargariy". The so-called "Islamic" composition is also popular in Tashkent.

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